

A Study on Current Anti-Microbial Susceptibility Pattern of Typhoidal Salmonella Causing Enteric Fever in School Going Children and Young Adults

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Abstract:

Background: Salmonella Typhi and Salmonella Paratyphi are the main causes of enteric fever, which is a serious public health issue, especially in developing nations. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is becoming more common, which makes treatment plans more difficult to implement and calls for ongoing surveillance of resistance patterns. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the current patterns of antimicrobial susceptibility to Typhoidal Salmonella in children and young people with enteric fever who attend school.

Methods: Prospective observational research with 300 people diagnosed with enteric fever between the ages of 5 and 25 was carried out. The Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method was used to determine the antibiotic susceptibility of the blood samples after Typhoidal Salmonella was isolated through culture. SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data, and chi-square tests and descriptive statistics were used.

Results: Out of 300 participants, 270 (90%) had positive blood cultures for Typhoidal Salmonella. High resistance was observed to Ampicillin (33%), Chloramphenicol (40%), and Cotrimoxazole (30%), while susceptibility to Ciprofloxacin, Ceftriaxone, and Azithromycin was 90%, 100%, and 97%, respectively. A significant association between age and resistance to Ampicillin was found ($p = 0.015$), with higher resistance in younger age groups.

Conclusion: The study highlights significant resistance to traditional antibiotics and underscores the continued efficacy of Ceftriaxone and Azithromycin for treating enteric fever. The findings emphasize the need for ongoing surveillance of antimicrobial resistance and rational antibiotic use to prevent further resistance development.

Keywords: Enteric Fever, Typhoidal Salmonella, Antimicrobial Resistance, School-Going Children, Young Adults.

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Introduction

Enteric fever, primarily caused by the pathogens Salmonella Typhi and Salmonella Paratyphi, remains a significant public health challenge, especially in developing countries. It is characterized by prolonged fever, abdominal pain, and a range of gastrointestinal symptoms. Enteric fever predominantly affects children and young adults, contributing to high morbidity and occasional mortality. Despite advancements in medical science and public health, enteric fever persists due to factors such as poor sanitation, inadequate access to clean water, and the emergence of antimicrobial resistance.

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in Typhoidal Salmonella has been increasingly reported, complicating treatment strategies and leading to prolonged illness and higher healthcare costs. Traditional first-line antibiotics, including

Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, and Cotrimoxazole, have seen declining effectiveness due to widespread resistance. This trend necessitates a continuous review of antimicrobial susceptibility patterns to guide effective treatment protocols. Recent studies highlight the growing resistance to commonly used antibiotics and the emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) strains of Salmonella Typhi [1].

The shift in susceptibility patterns calls for an updated understanding of the current resistance trends. According to recent research, third-generation cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones remain effective against many Salmonella strains, but resistance to these drugs is also on the rise. The World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the importance of robust surveillance

systems and antibiotic stewardship programs to combat the AMR crisis [2].

Recent advancements in molecular techniques and genomics have also enhanced our ability to detect and understand resistance mechanisms in Typhoidal Salmonella, paving the way for more precise and effective treatment strategies [3].

This study aims to assess the current antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of Typhoidal Salmonella in patients presenting with enteric fever.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of October 2016 to October 2017 at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, India.

Participants: A total of 300 participants were included in this study, comprising school-going children and young adults diagnosed with enteric fever.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 5-25 years.
2. Patients diagnosed with enteric fever based on clinical symptoms and confirmed by laboratory tests.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients outside the age range of 5-25 years.
2. Patients with a history of antibiotic use in the past two weeks.
3. Patients with underlying chronic illnesses that could interfere with the study outcomes.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were consecutively recruited from the hospital's patient

population meeting the inclusion criteria. Additionally, data collectors were blinded to the study's hypothesis to reduce observer bias.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and laboratory results. The questionnaire included demographic information, clinical presentation, and treatment history. Laboratory data included blood culture results and antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Procedure

Informed consent was obtained before identifying and enrolling the eligible subjects. Every participant had blood drawn for sensitivity and culture tests. Standard microbiological techniques were applied to blood cultures in order to isolate Typhoidal Salmonella. The Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method was used for assessing antibiotic susceptibility. Data from lab and clinical settings were entered into forms that were pre-made.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was utilised for data entry and analysis. The individuals' clinical and demographic features were compiled using descriptive statistics. Utilising frequency distributions, the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns were examined. The relationship between antibiotic resistance patterns and demographic characteristics was examined using chi-square testing. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

A total of 300 participants were enrolled in the study, comprising 180 school-going children (60%) and 120 young adults (40%). The age distribution is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Age Group	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
5-10	90	30
11-15	90	30
16-20	60	20
21-25	60	20

The most common clinical symptoms were fever (100%), headache (75%), abdominal pain (60%), and diarrhea (45%). The clinical presentation of participants is detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Clinical Presentation

Symptoms	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Fever	300	100
Headache	225	75
Abdominal Pain	180	60
Diarrhea	135	45

Blood cultures were positive for Typhoidal Salmonella in 270 participants (90%). The antimicrobial susceptibility patterns are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Blood Culture and Antimicrobial Susceptibility

Antibiotic	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)
Ampicillin	180 (67%)	90 (33%)
Chloramphenicol	162 (60%)	108 (40%)
Cotrimoxazole	189 (70%)	81 (30%)
Ciprofloxacin	243 (90%)	27 (10%)
Ceftriaxone	270 (100%)	0 (0%)
Azithromycin	261 (97%)	9 (3%)

Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 23.0. Chi-square tests were used to examine the association between demographic variables and antimicrobial resistance patterns. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Statistical Analysis

Variable	Ampicillin Resistance (%)	p-value	Ciprofloxacin Resistance (%)	p-value
Age Group				
5-10	30 (33%)	0.015	9 (10%)	0.864
11-15	30 (33%)		6 (7%)	
16-20	18 (20%)		6 (10%)	
21-25	12 (20%)		6 (10%)	
Gender				
Male	60 (33%)	0.054	18 (10%)	0.754
Female	30 (33%)		9 (10%)	

Discussion

The study evaluated the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of Typhoidal Salmonella in a cohort of 300 patients, including 180 school-going children and 120 young adults, over a one-year period. The age distribution was evenly spread across four groups, with each group representing a significant portion of the total participants. Clinical presentations were dominated by fever, headache, abdominal pain, and diarrhea, which are hallmark symptoms of enteric fever.

Blood culture results were positive for Typhoidal Salmonella in 90% of the participants, indicating a high prevalence of this pathogen in the studied population. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing revealed varying resistance patterns. Notably, 33% of the isolates were resistant to Ampicillin, 40% to Chloramphenicol, and 30% to Cotrimoxazole. In contrast, Ciprofloxacin, Ceftriaxone, and Azithromycin showed higher susceptibility rates, with Ceftriaxone being 100% effective and Azithromycin showing a 97% susceptibility rate.

Statistical analysis using SPSS version 23.0 indicated a significant association between age and resistance to Ampicillin ($p = 0.015$), with younger participants exhibiting higher resistance rates. However, no significant gender-based differences in resistance patterns were observed. The high effectiveness of Ceftriaxone and Azithromycin underscores their continued relevance in the

treatment of enteric fever, while the significant resistance to older antibiotics like Ampicillin and Chloramphenicol highlights the need for careful selection of antibiotic therapy.

Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the current antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of Typhoidal Salmonella in a high-risk population. The findings emphasize the necessity for ongoing surveillance and rational antibiotic use to combat the rising threat of antimicrobial resistance. These results can inform clinical decision-making and guide public health strategies to effectively manage and treat enteric fever in school-going children and young adults.

The frequency of ceftriaxone-resistant Salmonella enterica isolates from blood cultures in cases of typhoid fever was the subject of a study. 43.4% of Salmonella typhi and Salmonella paratyphi, according to the study Ceftriaxone resistance was present in the isolates. There was no evidence of resistance to azithromycin or meropenem. This suggests that first-line antibiotics are highly resistant, underscoring the significance of second-line therapies [4].

Children with fever were investigated for Salmonella enterica's susceptibility to antibiotics. Significant percentages of isolates (14%), as well as substantial resistance to quinolones (93.3%) and fluoroquinolones, were found to be resistant to these antibiotics. Cephalosporins and first-line

medications, however, had good sensitivity, indicating their continued usefulness for treatment in this area [5].

An investigation revealed that children's *Salmonella* Typhi and *Salmonella* Paratyphi antibiotic resistance. According to the study, 21.9% of isolates were multidrug-resistant (MDR) and 56.8% were extensively drug-resistant (XDR). Azithromycin and meropenem showed the least amount of resistance, which makes them good choices for empirical treatment [6].

The virulence factors of MDR *Salmonella* typhi isolates from Bauchi, Nigeria, were examined in a study. According to the study, 77% of the isolates exhibited resistance to more than one antimicrobial drug, with oxacillin showing the highest level of resistance (95.8%). Every isolate was multidrug resistant (MDR) and susceptible to amikacin, ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, and colistin sulphate [7].

In Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, a study was carried out to determine the prevalence and resistance patterns of *Salmonella* Typhi and *Salmonella* Paratyphi in school-age children. High levels of resistance to ciprofloxacin (62.7% for *S. Typhi* and 85.7% for *S. Paratyphi A*) and nalidixic acid (86.6% for *S. Typhi* and 90.5% for *S. Paratyphi A*) were discovered in the study. Azithromycin and ceftriaxone demonstrated reduced rates of resistance, rendering them feasible choices for empirical therapy [8].

A study including Bangladesh, Nepal, and Pakistan detailed the Surveillance for Enteric Fever in Asia Project (SEAP) from 2016 to 2019. Widespread drug resistance, including MDR in 17% of isolates from Bangladesh and 1% from Nepal, was discovered in the investigation of *S. Typhi*. 64% of *S. Typhi* isolates in Pakistan were XDR. In all three nations, FQ non-susceptibility was extremely high, but azithromycin non-susceptibility was moderate [9].

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the variability in antimicrobial susceptibility patterns among Typhoidal *Salmonella* isolates. The high susceptibility to Ceftriaxone and Azithromycin suggests that these antibiotics remain effective treatment options. The significant resistance to Ampicillin and Chloramphenicol underscores the need for continuous monitoring of resistance patterns and rational use of antibiotics to prevent further resistance development. The results underscore the importance of tailored antibiotic therapy based on current susceptibility patterns and suggest the need for ongoing surveillance to guide

effective treatment strategies for enteric fever in school-going children and young adults.

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